

Kostanecki-Robinson Acylation of Methyl-2, 4-Dihydroxy-5-Valerylbenzoate, Methyl-2, 4-Dihydroxy-3-Butyrylbenzoate and 3, 5-Dibromo-resacetophenone

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Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-5-valerylbenzoate, methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate and 3,5-dibromo-resacetophenone, propionylation of methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-5-valerylbenzoate and methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate and benzoylation of methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate have been studied. The various chromone and flavone derivatives were obtained. The chymone structure has been assigned to these products on the basis of the results obtained from the hydrolysis of the hydroxy-carboxy chromone derivatives with sodium hydroxide (10 %) to known *o*-hydroxybenzoic acid derivatives.

In continuation of our previous work¹, Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-5-valerylbenzoate, methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate and 3,5-dibromo-resacetophenone has been carried out. Propionylation of methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-5-valerylbenzoate and methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate and benzoylation of methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate have also been studied in the present work.

Methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-5-valerylbenzoate (I) was prepared in good yields by Friedel Crafts valerylation of methyl β -resorcylate with aluminium chloride and valeryl chloride². The ketone (I) when refluxed with fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride furnished 7-acetoxy-6-carbomethoxy-2-methyl-3-propylchromone (II), hydrolysis of which with ammonium hydroxide (2*N*) afforded 7-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-2-methyl-3-propylchromone (III). 7-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-2-methyl-3-propylchromone (IV) was obtained on alkali treatment (NaOH 5%) of the chromone (III) in cold. In order to confirm the chromone structure assigned to these products chromone (IV) was decarboxylated with copper in quinoline to the known 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-3-propylchromone³ (V). On treatment with sodium hydroxide (10%) in cold, the chromones (II), (III) and (IV) directly yielded, 2,4-dihydroxy-5-valerylbenzoic acid (VI) suggesting the rupture of γ -pyrone ring of the chromone.

Methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate (VII) was obtained in fairly good yields by Friedel Crafts butyrylation of methyl β -resorcylate with aluminium chloride and butyric anhydride². The ketone (VII) on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation furnished

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5-acetoxy-6-carbomethoxy-2-methyl-3-ethylchromone (VIII). On hydrolysis with ammonium hydroxide (2*N*) chromone (VIII) yielded 5-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-2-methyl-3-ethylchromone (IX), while 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-2-methyl-3-ethylchromone (X) was obtained on alkali hydrolysis (NaOH 5%) in cold. In order to confirm the chromone structure assigned to these products, chromone (X) was decarboxylated with copper in quinoline to the known 5-hydroxy-2-methyl-3-ethylchromone⁴ (XI). On treatment with sodium hydroxide (10%) in cold, chromones (VIII), (IX) and (X) directly yielded, 2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoic acid (XII) suggesting the rupture of α -pyrone ring of the chromone.

Similarly methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-5-valerylbenzoate (I) and methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate (VII) on Kostanecki-Robinson propionylation furnished crude propionoxycarbomethoxychromone derivatives, which on treatment with ammonium hydroxide (2*N*) yielded 7-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-2-ethyl-3-propylchromone (XIII) and 5-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-2,3-diethylchromone (XV) respectively. Hydrolysis of the chromones (XIII) and (XV) with sodium hydroxide (5%) afforded 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-2-ethyl-3-propylchromone (XIV) and 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-2,3-diethylchromone (XVI) respectively. The chromone (XIII), (XIV), (XV), and (XVI) on further hydrolysis with sodium hydroxide (10%) directly yielded 2,4-dihydroxy-5-valerylbenzoic acid (VI) and 2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoic acid (XII) respectively.

The chromone structure has been assigned to these compounds on the basis of the results of the hydrolysis of the hydroxy-carboxychromone derivatives with sodium hydroxide (10%) to known *o*-hydroxybenzoic acid derivatives, Kostanecki-Robinson acylation of methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-5-butyryl and 5-propionylbenzoates⁴ and Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-5-propionylbenzoate by Desai, Desai and Desai⁵.

3,5-Dibromo-resacetophenone (XVII) was prepared in good yields by bromination of resacetophenone⁶. The ketone (XVII) on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation furnished 7-acetoxy-6,8-dibromo-2-methyl-3-acetylchromone (XVIII). Hydrolysis of the chromone (XVIII) with concentrated sulphuric acid afforded 7-hydroxy-6,8-dibromo-2-methyl-3-acetylchromone (XIX). In order to confirm the chromone structure given to the compounds, deacetylation of chromone (XIX) was carried out with sodium carbonate (5%), when the known 7-hydroxy-6,8-dibromo-2-methylchromone (XX) was obtained⁷. The known 3,5-dibromo-resacetophenone (XVII) was obtained when chromone (XIX) was heated with Sodium hydroxide (10%) suggesting the rupture of γ -pyrone ring of the chromone. 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones of the chromones (XVIII) and (XIX) were also synthesised confirming the presence of acetyl group in 3rd position.

On similar Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation of methyl-2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoate (VII) afforded 5-benzoyloxy-6-carbomethoxy-3-ethylflavone (XXI). On keeping the flavone (XXI) with either ammonium hydroxide (2*N*) or sodium hydroxide (5%) no definite product was obtained. The hydrolysis of flavone (XXI) therefore was carried out with concentrated sulphuric acid when it gave 5-hydroxy-6-carboxy-3-ethylflavone (XXII). 2,4-Dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoic acid (XII) was obtained when flavone (XXII) was heated with sodium hydroxide (10%) on boiling water bath for five hours, suggesting the rupture of γ -pyrone ring of the flavone.

Details regarding the above mentioned compounds are given in the accompanying Tables Nos. I to VI.

I to VI	$\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	$\text{R}_1 = \text{CH}_3$	$\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$	$\text{R}_3 = \text{OH}$	$\text{R}_4 = \text{H}$	$\text{R}_5 = \text{H}$
VII to XII	$\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	$\text{R}_1 = \text{CH}_3$	$\text{R}_2 = \text{OH}$	$\text{R}_3 = \text{H}$	$\text{R}_4 = \text{OCOCH}_3$	$\text{R}_5 = \text{OCOCH}_3$
XIII to XIV	$\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	$\text{R}_1 = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	$\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$	$\text{R}_3 = \text{OH}$	$\text{R}_4 = \text{OCOCH}_3$	$\text{R}_5 = \text{H}$
XV to XVI	$\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	$\text{R}_1 = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	$\text{R}_2 = \text{OH}$	$\text{R}_3 = \text{H}$	$\text{R}_4 = \text{H}$	$\text{R}_5 = \text{H}$
XXI to XX	$\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	$\text{R}_1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	$\text{R}_2 = \text{OH}$	$\text{R}_3 = \text{H}$	$\text{R}_4 = \text{OCOC}_6\text{H}_5$	$\text{R}_5 = \text{H}$

XVII to XX $\text{R} = \text{R}_1 = \text{CH}_3$

TABLE I
Kostanecki-Robinson Reaction Products

Ketone	K.R. Reaction	Product obtained	M.P. °C	Yield (g.)	FeCl ₃ test.	Mol. For.	% of C, H, Br
Methyl-2 : 4-dihydroxy- 5-valerylbenzoate.	Acetylation	7-Acetoxy-6-carbomethoxy- 2-methyl-3-propyl- chromone.*	105-08	1.00	No colour	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₆	Reqd. C : 64.15 Found C : 63.98 Reqd. H : 5.66 Found H : 5.55
	Propionylation	Crude product.	—	—	—	—	—
Methyl-2 : 4-dihydroxy- 3-butyrylbenzoate.	Acetylation	5-Acetoxy-6-carbomethoxy 2-methyl-3-ethyl- chromone.	112-14	0.75	No colour	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₆	Reqd. C : 63.15 Found C : 62.95 Reqd. H : 5.26 Found H : 5.10
	Propionylation	Crude product	—	—	—	—	—
	Benzoylation	5-Benzoyloxy-6-carb- methoxy 3-ethyl flavone	144-45	0.7	No colour	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₆	Reqd. C : 72.89 Found C : 72.75 Reqd. H : 4.67 Found H : 4.54
3 : 5-Dibromo-resaceto- phenone.	Acetylation	7-Acetoxy-6 : 8-dibromo 2-methyl-3-acetyl- chromone.**	144-46	0.55	No colour	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃ Br ₂	Reqd. C : 40.19 Found C : 39.99 Reqd. H : 2.89 Found H : 2.28 Reqd. Br : 38.27 Found Br : 38.16

*I.R. (Nujol) 1750cm⁻¹ (—OCOCH₃), 1700cm⁻¹ (—COOCH₃), 1640cm⁻¹ (chromone (C = O))

** , , 1770cm⁻¹ (—OCOCH₃), 1640cm⁻¹ (chromone C = O)

TABLE II

Hydrolysis of 7-Acyloxy-6-carbomethoxychromone derivatives with NH₄OH (2N)

Acyloxy-carbomethoxy chromone derivative	Chromone obtained on hydrolysis	M.P. °C	Yield (g)	FeCl ₃ test	Mol. For.	% of C and H
7-Acetoxy-6-carb-methoxy 2-methyl-3-propylchromone.	7-Hydroxy-6-carb-methoxy 2-methyl-3-propylchromone.*	108-10	0.45	Red colour	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₅	Reqd. C: 65.21 Found C: 65.09 Reqd. H: 5.79 Found H: 5.59
Crude Acyloxy product from propionylation.	7-Hydroxy-6-carb-methoxy 2-ethyl-3-propylchromone.**	125-28	0.7	Red colour	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₅	Reqd. C: 66.2 Found C: 66.05 Reqd. H: 6.2 Found H: 6.1
5-Acetoxy-6-carb-methoxy 2-methyl-3-ethylchromone.	5-Hydroxy-6-carb-methoxy 2-methyl-3-ethylchromone.	108-10	0.35	Red colour	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₅	Reqd. C: 64.12 Found C: 64.02 Reqd. H: 5.34 Found H: 5.20
Crude Acyloxy product from propionylation.	5-Hydroxy-6-carb-methoxy 2 : 3-diethylchromone.	75-78	0.75	Red colour	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₅	Reqd. C: 65.21 Found C: 65.1 Reqd. H: 5.79 Found H: 5.65

*I.R. (Nujol) 1680cm⁻¹ (-COOCH₃) ; 1650cm⁻¹ (chromone C = O)
 ** ,, ,, 1675cm⁻¹ ,, ; 1640cm⁻¹ ,, .

TABLE III

Hydrolysis of 7-Hydroxy-6-carbomethoxychromone derivatives with NaOH (5%)

Hydroxy-carbomethoxy-chromone derivative	Chromone obtained on hydrolysis	M.P. °C	Yield (g)	FeCl ₃ test	Mol. For.	% of C and H
7-Hydroxy-6-carb-methoxy 2-methyl-3-propylchromone.	7-Hydroxy-6-carboxy 2-methyl-3-propyl-chromone.*	238-40	0.4	Red colour	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₅	Reqd. C: 64.12 Found C: 64.00 Reqd. H: 5.34 Found H: 5.21
7-Hydroxy-6-carb-methoxy 2-ethyl-3-propylchromone.	7-Hydroxy-6-carboxy 2-ethyl-3-propyl-chromone.**	190-92	0.39	Red colour	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₅	Reqd. C: 65.21 Found C: 65.09 Reqd. H: 5.79 Found H: 5.65
5-Hydroxy-6-carb-methoxy 2-methyl-3-ethylchromone.	5-Hydroxy-6-carboxy 2-methyl-3-ethyl-chromone.	185-88	0.25	Red colour	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₅	Reqd. C: 62.90 Found C: 62.85 Reqd. H: 4.83 Found H: 4.65
5-Hydroxy-6-carb-methoxy 2 : 3-diethylchromone.	5-Hydroxy-6-carboxy 2 : 3-diethylchromone.	138-39	0.15	Red colour	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₅	Reqd. C: 64.12 Found C: 63.95 Reqd. H: 5.34 Found H: 5.30

*I.R. (Nujol) 1675cm⁻¹ (-COOCH₃) ; 1630cm⁻¹ (chromone C = O)
 ** ,, ,, 1680cm⁻¹ (-COOH) ; 1635cm⁻¹ (chromone C = O)

TABLE IV(A)

Hydrolysis of Hydroxy-carboxychromone derivatives with NaOH (10%)

Hydroxy-carboxychromone derivative	Formation of <i>o</i> -hydroxy benzoic acid	M.P. °C	Yield (g)
7-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-2-methyl-3-propylchromone.	2 : 4-Dihydroxy-5-valerylbenzoic acid	175-76	0.2
7-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-2-ethyl-3-propylchromone.	2 : 4-Dihydroxy-5-butyrylbenzoic acid	150-51	0.2
5-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-2-methyl-3-ethylchromone	2 : 4-Dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoic acid	150-51	0.2
5-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-2 : 3-diethylchromone			

TABLE IV(B)

Hydrolysis of Hydroxyflavone and Hydroxychromone derivatives by heating with NaOH (10%) for five hours

Hydroxyflavone and hydroxy-chromone derivative	Product obtained	M.P. °C	Yield (g.)
5-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-3-ethylflavone.	2 : 4-Dihydroxy-3-butyrylbenzoic acid	150-51	0.15
7-Hydroxy-6 : 8-dibromo-2-methyl-3-acetylchromone	3 : 5-Dibromo resacetophenone	174-75	0.10

TABLE V

Hydrolysis of Acyloxyflavone and Acyloxychromone derivatives with conc. H₂SO₄

Acyloxyflavone and Acyloxychromone derivative	Chromone derivative obtained	M.P. °C	Yield (g.)	FeCl ₃ test	Mol. For.	% of C, H and Br
5-Benzoyloxy-6-carbomethoxy-3-ethylflavone.	5-Hydroxy-6-carboxy 3-ethylflavone	158-60	0.18	Red colour	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₅	Reqd. C: 69.67 Found C: 69.50 Reqd. H: 4.51 Found H: 4.45
7-Acetoxy-6 : 8-dibromo-2-methyl-3-acetylchromone.	7-Hydroxy-6 : 8-dibromo 2-methyl-3-acetylchromone.*	225-26	0.75	Redish brown colour	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₅ Br ₂	Reqd. C: 38.29 Found C: 38.14 Reqd. H: 2.12 Found H: 2.10 Reqd. Br: 42.55 Found Br: 42.36

*I.R. (Nujol) 1635cm⁻¹ (chromone C = O)

TABLE VI

2 : 4-Dinitro-phenylhydrazone derivatives

Acylchromone derivative	Product obtained	M.P °C	Mol. For.	% of N
7-Acetoxy-6 : 8-dibromo- 2-methyl-3-acetylchromone (XVIII).	2 : 4-Dinitrophenyl- hydrazone derivative of (XVIII).	224-25	$C_{20}H_{14}O_8Br_2N_4$	Reqd. N: 9.36 Found N: 9.05
7-Hydroxy-6 : 8-dibromo- 2-methyl-3-acetylchromone (XIX).	2 : 4-Dinitrophenyl- hydrazone derivative of (XIX).	255-56	$C_{18}H_{12}O_7Br_2N_4$	Reqd. N: 10.07 Found N: 9.98

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